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Impact of Brainstorming Instructional Strategy on Science-Process-Skills of Biology Students in Secondary Schools of Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the impact of brainstorming instructional strategy on science process skills of biology students in secondary schools of Zamfara state, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study which adopted the pretest, posttest non-randomized control group quasi-experimental design. The target population of the study was a total of 25,335 (16,395 male; 8,940 female) SS2 students while the sample was 115 (62 male; 53 female) students in the state. Multi-stage sampling was used in selecting 2 schools for the study. The experimental group was exposed to brainstorming instructional strategy, whereas the control group was taught using conventional method. Cellular respiration was the biological concept treated while Science Process Skills Inventory (SPSI) was the research instrument used. Three experts validated the SPSI and its reliability index was 0.82 using test-retest method and Cronbach Alpha tool. The data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and One-Way ANCOVA statistical tools at 0.05 significant level. The result of the study revealed that the experimental group students gained higher science process skills than those in the control group. It was also found that there was no significant gender interaction effect on science process skills of the students exposed to the strategy. Thus, it was concluded that the strategy enhances students' science process skills and is gender-friendly. It was therefore recommended that biology teachers should adopt the strategy to improve students' acquisition and utilization of the science process skills, learning outcomes and ways of doing science.

Keywords: Brainstorming, Strategy, Science-Process Skills, Biology

Introduction

Biology being life science serves as a pivotal science subject offered in senior secondary schools and remains prerequisite for admission into tertiary institutions of higher learning especially for medical, pharmaceutical, biotechnological, agricultural and Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) courses. Adekali (2023) asserted that biological knowledge offers multifaceted and highly

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significant roles that impact the universe and all living matters existing on earth from time immemorial to the future. It has contributed tremendously to financial, physical and aesthetic benefits of mankind and nation-building.

However, despite the importance of biology, statistics of grades obtained by biology candidates in the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) examination in the recent years have not been encouraging (WAEC Chief Examiner's Report, 2020-2024; Nwagbo, 2019). That is why biology is losing its might in academic performance of students in post-primary institutions (Ekineh & Otuturu, 2024). Biology is a very vast branch of science with diversified branches, topics and concepts like botany, zoology, microbiology, anatomy, physiology, genetics, biochemistry, biotechnology, cytology and cellular respiration.

Cellular respiration is the process by which cells convert glucose into energy in the form of adenosine triphosphates (ATP) which are molecular units for energy transfer in the body of organisms. Respiration is the process by which complex food substances are broken down, in a stepwise series of reactions, in cells, to produce energy with carbon dioxide and water as waste products (Dam *et al.*, 2019). Cellular or tissue respiration involves the chemical activities of the cells in which glucose is broken down by a series of reactions controlled by enzymes to release energy. It is very essential for the survival of living organisms, as it provides the energy needed to power cellular activities.

Its main function is to synthesize biochemical energy (in the form of ATP) which is stored and used by all living cells for the various metabolic processes such as biosynthesis, locomotion, reproduction, nutrition, response, growth, excretion, gaseous exchange and transportation of molecules across membranes and so forth (Usman, 2021). Hence, life could virtually cease to exist without cellular respiration processes occurring smoothly in the bodies of organisms.

Isma'il and Lukman (2023) indicated that biology presents distinct challenges to students owing to its intricate and abstract nature. Cellular processes and genetics are complex concepts that can prove difficult to grasp solely through traditional teaching methods. Cellular respiration is also identified among the perceived difficult topics in senior secondary school biology curriculum in Zamfara state (Isma'il & Matazu, 2024). It is so wide with varied abstract contents or ideas that could best be taught using student-centered instructions like the BIS in order to enhance students' performance and science-process skills.

Science Process Skills (SPS) are cognitive and psychomotor skills which scientists employ in problem identification, objective inquiry, data gathering, transformation, interpretation and communication of scientific facts and discoveries. They are special skills that learners and teachers use in carrying out mental operations and physical activities in the field of science (Segun & Akanbi, 2023). SPS include: observing, measuring, classifying, predicting, inferring, hypothesizing, testing/experiments, interpreting and communicating.

The significance of the SPS has led to the expansion of the goals of science education to include an understanding and development in the students of these process skills (Flavia, Bernard & Eugenia,

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2022). The SPS, motivation and performance are among the important variables of great concern by educational researchers who are mostly keenly interested in determining gender effects in their varied studies. Hence, modern teaching is based on student-centered instruction such as the brainstorming instructional strategy.

Brainstorming Instructional Strategy (BIS) is a strategy that organizes learners into participatory small or large groups that indulge in critical thinking which could enhance free flow of ideas among them as they interact with the teacher. It is a special way to develop creative thinking as it peculiarly involves working on flow of ideas without criticism as participation of the learners spread thinking and challenges their minds (Khan & Ashraf, 2021). On how best to adopt the BIS in the teaching and learning process, Bluedorn and Bluedorn (2014) and Khan and Ashraf (2021) offered a brainstorming model containing six elements or steps: (i) Pick a Question or Problem to Solve; (ii) Pick a Time and Place; (iii) Encourage Discussion and Ideas; (iv) Set a Time Limit; (v) Write all the Ideas Down and Organize; and (vi) Get Rid of Bad Ideas. When successfully incorporated in the teaching and learning process, the BIS helps in improving science students' motivation, SPS and performance for both gender.

Gender refers to the distinguishing attribute ascribed to male and female individuals based on biological features. Nda (2023) conceived gender as the range of physical, biological, mental and behavioural characteristics pertaining to and differentiating between the feminine and masculine (female and male) population. Recently, gender related issues in science education have generated serious concerns amongst varied educators judging by the number of studies done to that effect. Hence, gender is considered as one of the variables in this study in order to investigate its influence on students' SPS in biology. It was against this background therefore, the study investigated the impact of brainstorming instructional strategy on science-process skills in biology among secondary school students in Zamfara state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study was to investigate the impact of brainstorming instructional strategy on science-process skills in biology among secondary school students in Zamfara state, Nigeria. Specifically, it seeks to:

- i. Determine the impact of BIS on secondary school students' science-process skills in cellular respiration; and
- ii. Investigate gender interaction effect among secondary school students' science-process skills when exposed to the BIS in cellular respiration.

Research Questions

- i. To what extent does the BIS impact on secondary school students' science-process skills in cellular respiration?
- ii. Is there any gender interaction effect among secondary school students' science-process skills when exposed to the BIS in cellular respiration?

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Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: BIS does not significantly impact on secondary school students' science-process skills in Cellular Respiration.

H₀₂: There is no significant gender interaction effect among secondary school students' science-process skills when exposed to the BIS in Cellular Respiration.

Methodology

The pretest, posttest, non-randomized quasi-experimental design was the research design adopted in the study. Both the experimental and control groups were initially pretested to determine their equivalence in SPS in the cellular respiration concept. After the treatment, both groups were post-tested to determine the impacts of the treatment on their SPS in the concept treated.

The total population of the study was all the 112,577 (61,728 male; 50,849 female) senior secondary school students for the 2024/2025 session in all the 339 senior secondary schools (both public and private) in Zamfara state while the target population was only the 25,335 (16,395 males; 8,940 females) SS2 students in the schools (Zamfara State Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (ZSMEST), 2024; National Association of Proprietors of Private Schools (NAPPS) Zamfara State Chapter, 2024). All the urban public senior secondary schools are single-sex and gender was involved in the study. Hence, public-private partnership coeducational schools which share common characteristics with the public schools in the state were used to serve the purpose better. The SS-II students were used as intact classes because they were more stable in the schools than the SS-I and III students who are beginning to study the subject and facing their final exams respectively.

Multi-stage sampling was used in selecting the study's sample. This is because it is difficult for the researchers to cover the whole state and to avoid selection bias in the study. Simple random sampling by balloting was used to select two (2) out of the four (4) educational zones in the state. One (1) local government area was randomly selected by balloting from each of the two selected educational zones. Thereafter, purposive sampling (based on the need for coeducational schools) was used to select two (2) public-private partnership coeducational senior secondary schools (one from each of the selected local government areas). The schools were assigned as experimental and control groups using simple random sampling by tossing coin. Finally, an intact class from each of the experimental and control groups was chosen for the study also using simple random sampling by balloting.

The simple random sampling technique was appropriate due to the facts that: it is scientific in which all subjects have equal chances of either being selected or deselected as part of the study's sample. The purposive sampling technique was suitable as the study involved gender as one of its variables which requires the use of coeducational schools but the public senior secondary schools in the state are single-sex. The research instrument used in the study was Science Process Skills Inventory (SPSI) which was validated by three experts all in Federal University Gusau, Zamfara state, Nigeria. The validators' observations, corrections and suggestions led to the modifications of some of the SPSI items before the final draft. The instrument was pilot-tested using test-retest method and the scores were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha statistical tool which yielded a reliability coefficient (r) = 0.82.

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The researchers used the two distinct methods (BIS and conventional method) respectively in teaching the two different groups the concept of cellular respiration for a period of four (4) weeks as treatment and placebo for both the experimental and control groups during the normal biology periods in the sampled schools. Students in the experimental group were taught concept of cellular respiration with BIS, adhering strictly to the steps specified in its lesson plans in which the students varied ideas (right and wrong, good and bad) were accommodated, noted and finally refined by the teacher throughout the lessons. All the subjects in the control group were taught the same concept using the conventional method also for four (4) weeks, adhering to the steps in its lesson plans. The premise of this method is that the learner knows little/nothing about the content and so needs to be told, should watch, should listen attentively and take down relevant notes all from the teacher.

Finally, posttest was administered to both the experimental and control group after the treatments. The scores of both groups were recorded (male and female separately) and analyzed using descriptive (mean and standard deviation) and inferential (One-Way ANCOVA) statistics at significance level of $P \leq 0.05$ for answering the research questions and testing the null hypotheses respectively with SPSS version 25.0.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does the BIS impact on secondary school students' science process skills in cellular respiration? This research question was answered using mean and standard deviation as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of the Result of Students' Posttest SPS Scores Means and Standard Deviations for both Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean (\bar{X})	SD	Std. Error Mean	MD	Remarks
Experimental	59	27.66	7.92	1.04		
Control	56	21.17	7.43	1.43	6.49	Difference Exists
Total	115					

Table 1 above revealed that the mean SPS scores of the experimental and control groups were 27.66 and 21.17 respectively with the mean difference of 6.49. It could clearly be seen that the experimental group had higher SPS than the control group. This could largely be attributed to the treatment/intervention (that is the exposure to the BIS) given to the experimental group in the study. However, by their respective standard deviations, the students' SPS scores in the control group were more closely around the mean compared to those of the experimental group.

Hypothesis 1

BIS does not significantly impact on secondary school students' science-process skills in Cellular Respiration. To test this hypothesis, the mean SPS scores of the experimental and control group

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students were compared using One-Way ANCOVA at $P \leq 0.05$ and the pretest as the covariate. The result obtained is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of One-Way ANCOVA of Students' SPS Scores in SPSI

Source	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	15245.594	4	3811.398	30.777*	.000	
Intercept	45302.745	1	45302.745	365.815*	.000	
Pre-test	31.012	1	31.012	0.250	.618	Not Sign.
Inst. Strategy	14469.023	1	14469.023	116.836*	.000	Sign.
Error	13993.974	113	123.840			
Total	424685.000	118				
Corrected Total	29239.568	117				

* Significant ($P < 0.05$)

The result from Table 2 showed that the BIS is statistically significant at P -value of .000 and therefore it is also statistically significant at a higher P -value of .05. Thus the null hypothesis which stated that BIS does not significantly impact on secondary school students' science process skills in cellular respiration is hereby rejected. Thus, the inference drawn is that there is a statistically significant difference between the mean SPS scores of secondary school students taught cellular respiration concept using BIS and those taught using conventional method of teaching in favour of the experimental group ($F = 116.836^*$, $df = 1$ and $P = .000 < .05$).

Research Question 2

Is there any gender interaction effect among secondary school students' science-process skills when exposed to the BIS in Cellular Respiration? This research question was also answered using mean and standard deviation as shown in table 3.

Table 3: Summary of the Result of Students' Posttest SPS Scores Means and Standard Deviations in the Experimental Group by Gender

Gender	N	Mean (\bar{X})	SD	Std. Error Mean	MD	Remarks
Male	31	16.02	2.44	0.89	0.04	No Difference
Female	28	15.98	2.75	0.90		
Total	59					

Table 4.3 showed that the posttest SPS scores means and standard deviations of male students in the experimental group were 16.02 and 2.57 respectively while those of the female students were 15.98 and 2.47 respectively. Hence, there was no difference in the mean posttest SPS scores of the male and female students exposed to BIS. This means that both male and female students achieved equal higher SPS and this can be attributed to the nature of the treatment (exposure to the BIS) they received.

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However, in terms of their standard deviations, the scores of the male students were more closely around the mean compared to those of the female students.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant gender interaction effect among secondary school students' science-process skills when exposed to the BIS in cellular respiration. To test this hypothesis, the mean SPS scores of male and female students in the experimental group were compared using One-Way ANCOVA at $P \leq 0.05$ and the pretest as the covariate. The result obtained is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of One-Way ANCOVA of Students' SPS Scores in SPSI by Gender

Source	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	15245.594	4	3811.398	30.777*	.000	
Intercept	45302.745	1	45302.745	365.815*	.000	
Pre-test	31.012	1	31.012	0.250	.618	Not Sign.
Gender	260.389	1	260.389	2.103	.150	Not Sign.
Error	13993.974	113	123.840			
Total	424685.000	118				
Corrected Total	29239.568	117				

* Significant ($P < 0.05$)

Table 4 revealed that the computed F -ratio for gender interaction effect on students' SPS in the cellular respiration concept taught was 2.103 which is not significant at P -value of .05. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant gender interaction effect among secondary school students' science process skills when exposed to the BIS in cellular respiration was retained being that the derived significant level is greater than the α -value (F -ratio = 2.103, $df = 1$ and $P = .150 > .05$). Thus, the inference drawn is that BIS is gender-friendly as it favours both gender in teaching the concept of cellular respiration at senior secondary level.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study indicated that the students taught cellular respiration concept of biology with the BIS gained higher mean SPS score which was statistically significant than that of the students taught using the conventional method. This finding agreed with that of Khan and Ashraf (2021) who revealed that students instructed using BIS got ample opportunity to express their ideas, concepts, thought and knowledge which develops creativity, critical thinking, collaboration, communication and problem solving skills. They could observe, read, collect and accumulate information and discuss it in the classroom with their peer group and teachers. They use the skills learned in the classroom in the external world observations and experiences. It also confirms the findings of Wagbara (2020), Malkawi and Al-Balqa (2018) and Mohammed (2016) who found that BIS had significant effect on students' mean achievement score as there were significant differences between the mean achievement scores of students exposed to the strategy in and those of lecture method in favor of brainstorming strategy.

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On gender interaction effect, the study revealed equal mean SPS scores by both male and female students taught cellular respiration using the BIS as there was no statistically significant mean difference in their respective SPS scores. Hence, the finding showed that gender has no effect in learning cellular respiration concept of biology among students when exposed to the BIS. This finding confirms that of Wagbara (2020) who revealed that gender does not have significant effect on students taught Chemistry by use of brainstorming strategy. The finding however disagreed with those of Mohammed (2016) and Malkawi and Al-Balqua, (2018) who stated that there is significant difference between the male and female students taught by the use of brainstorming strategy in favor of the females.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that the use of the brainstorming instructional strategy enhanced the acquisition and utilization of biology students' science process skills in learning cellular respiration concept. Also, the strategy is gender-friendly as it favours both male and female students at senior secondary school level.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study.

1. Biology teachers should adopt the use of the brainstorming instructional strategy in teaching the subject for the students to have better science process skills which will help them in achieving better learning outcomes and doing science well.
2. Brainstorming instructional strategy should be incorporated into the science teachers' training curriculum in our teacher training institutions so as to produce professionally qualified teachers capable of using the strategy well in their teaching practices in schools.
3. Professional Associations such as Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) and Governments at different levels should guide the teachers on how to use the strategy through seminars, retraining and provision of adequate teaching aids to facilitate the smooth use of the strategy.

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